

Internal Migration In The Netherlands 2009-2022: Networks And Factors Of Migration Flows

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Abstract

This study examines internal migration in the Netherlands over the period from 2009 to 2022, providing insights into the magnitude, characteristics, and spatial patterns of movements between municipalities. Using comprehensive individual-level data from Statistics Netherlands (CBS), it explores demographic profiles of internal migrants, factors influencing mobility, and the structure of migration networks. The analysis draws on two main sources: the register-based node data of the Person Network of the Netherlands, covering the entire Dutch population, and the Social Cohesion and Well-being (SSW) survey, which provides detailed social indicators from a representative sample. Combining descriptive statistics, network analysis, and visualization techniques, the publication offers a detailed look at who moves, how far they move, and the reciprocal nature of migration flows across regions. The results highlight that internal migration significantly shapes demographic dynamics and regional development. Young adults, particularly those aged 20–30, are most mobile. This likely reflects educational transitions, early career development, and household formation, as these life stages tend to coincide with higher mobility. Additionally, educational attainment appears to be a major factor in migration rates, with the higher educated individuals showing higher mobility. Income also plays a role, as both the lowest and highest quartiles exhibit notable migration levels. A distinctive feature of the Dutch internal migration network is its high reciprocity—around 75% of migration flows are matched by reciprocal movements, reflecting relatively balanced exchanges among municipalities. Policymakers, researchers, and urban planners can use these insights to better understand population redistribution, address regional imbalances, and develop strategies that support sustainable community development across the Netherlands.

keywords: *Internal Migration in the Netherlands; Migration Complex Network; Migration Network Factors.*

Introduction

Migration plays a significant role in shaping the Netherlands' society. About one-quarter of people residing in the country are either first- or second-generation international migrants (foreign-born or children of foreign-born) (CBS, 2023). Yet, internal migration within the Netherlands is arguably even more influential on regional demographics. Globally, internal

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moves occur at roughly four times the volume of international moves (UNDP, 2009; IOM, 2020; McKenzie, 2022), a widespread and structurally significant phenomenon, as this paper demonstrates. Despite this, internal migration has received comparatively little attention in research and policy discussions, often overshadowed by immigration debates.

Few studies have specifically focused on internal migration in the Netherlands, particularly in the more recent periods. Early studies in the Netherlands found that individuals migrated more than families (Hofstee, 1954), distance deterred mobility (Masser, 1976), and migration likelihood depended on gender, cohort, birthplace, and socio-economic background (Sesma et al., 2022). Bartels & Liaw (1983) emphasized economic growth, employment, and housing supply, while later studies highlighted population size, urbanization, and age (Courgeau et al., 1989; Rees et al., 1998). Researchers also found that migration patterns varied by migrant background (CBS, 2002), and were influenced by family status, rural placement, and homeownership (de Hoon et al., 2021). University graduates were disproportionately mobile and concentrated in the Randstad, reinforcing spatial human capital disparities (Kooiman et al., 2018). Kooiman & Das (2022) showed that couple migration reflected education levels, occupations, family ties, and regional opportunities, with male education influencing long-distance moves more strongly. Other studies linked migration to divorce (Feijten & van Ham, 2007), unemployment and housing (Vermeulen & Verkade, 2003), rural preference (Bijker et al., 2012), family complexity (van der Wiel et al., 2021), neighbourhood dissatisfaction (de Jong, 2022), and commuting pressures (Biesenbeek, 2022). The studies are presented chronologically by the periods analysed, with only a few selected factors extracted; readers are referred to the original works for further detail given space limitations.

Overall, past research suggests a complex interplay of demographic, socio-economic, and contextual factors in internal migration decisions. For the Netherlands, the emphasis by researchers has been on gender, age, socio-economic status, housing availability, proximity to family and friends, life course events (s.a. marriage and divorce), population density, job availability, education level, birthplace, and religious affiliation. These factors have been shown to influence migration behaviour in various ways, with some factors like housing characteristics, urbanization, and economic conditions being more consistently identified across multiple studies, while others like family structure and the presence of non-resident children have been explored in more specific contexts.

However, these studies were limited in scope or dated, leaving a need for an up-to-date, comprehensive analysis. To fill this gap, our study examines internal migration within the Netherlands from 2009 through 2022 using detailed individual-level data of the whole population and its representative sample. Moreover, we offer a unique perspective on migration by applying network science and visualization techniques to uncover structural patterns and spatial dynamics that are not easily visible through traditional methods. In the following sections, we describe the data and methods, present the results of our network and statistical analyses of internal migration patterns, and discuss the implications of these findings.

Data and Methods

In migration research, three main forms of empirical evidence are typically used to assess driving or deterring factors: (1) inferential statistics, which match measured migration flows with estimated explanatory variables; (2) self-reported motivations gathered through surveys and interviews; and (3) direct observation, which is more limited due to the nature of migration being captured as a discrete event over a fixed interval (e.g. a move recorded in a given year). Of these, inferential statistical approaches are most commonly employed and are generally considered the most robust. However, as argued in Pitoski et al. (2024) and further demonstrated in this study, such approaches often carry substantial limitations—particularly

concerning how migration is operationalized and how network structures (e.g. looping edges and reciprocal flows) are treated analytically.

A key issue is that internal migration data often reflect a high degree of reciprocal movement between locations, as well as substantial volumes of return migration (i.e. self-loops). These patterns raise serious concerns about model specification, the choice of unit of analysis, and the validity of assigning explanatory power to either origin- or destination-specific characteristics. Standard migration modelling regresses flows from origin (O) to destination (D) on variables measured either at the link level (e.g. distance, contiguity, or differentials such as income gaps, which are derived from differences in variables defined separately at the origin and destination), or at the level of origin or destination alone (e.g. outflows explained by push factors at O, or inflows explained by pull factors at D). However, when migration networks are characterized by high reciprocity and looping, such models may obscure the structural nature of migration dynamics and introduce significant bias.

Given these concerns, this preliminary study—intended as the first in a broader series—deliberately avoids the use of inferential statistics. Instead, we adopt a descriptive approach, drawing on rich administrative and survey data to examine patterns of migration frequency, distance, and reciprocity, alongside core individual characteristics. Our objective is to clarify the structural features of internal migration in the Netherlands before moving toward causal modelling in future work.

This analysis utilizes two primary data sources from Statistics Netherlands (CBS). The first is the node data from the Person Network of the Netherlands (CBS, 2022), a comprehensive register-based dataset covering the entire population of the Netherlands. For each year from 2009 to 2022, it provides individual-level information including basic demographics (gender, age), socio-economic status (education level, income quartile), migration background (native or with foreign background), and place of residence (municipality). This enables tracking whether a person changed their municipality of residence from one year to the next, which we use to identify internal migration events. A total of over 4.7 million individuals in the Netherlands migrated at least once between 2009 and 2022, representing just over 25% of the country's 2022 population.

The second data source is the Social Cohesion and Well-being survey (SSW) (CBS 2024). The SSW is an annual nationally representative survey (about 7,600 respondents per year since 2012, totalling ~84,000 individuals) that collects rich information on social factors not available in registers. In addition to basic attributes (age, gender, education, income, etc.), the SSW includes variables on family and household composition, employment, health, religiosity, civic and social participation, trust, and subjective well-being. We used an extract of the SSW data up to 2022 ($N = 83,667$ respondents) and linked it to the Persons Network records. This linkage allowed us to study a subset of internal migrants (those who moved at least once, $N \approx 20,253$ in the SSW sample) with both their migration history and their social-characteristic indicators. SSW has recently been extended with a range of indicators derived from the Person Network (see Pitoski & Schmeets, 2026), to which we refer the reader for a clearer explanation of how the two databases are linked, as well as a more detailed description of the linkage procedure and the variables available.

For analysis, we applied a combination of descriptive statistics, network analysis, and visualization techniques. Descriptive statistics were used to examine how migration frequencies and distances vary across different groups and over time. Network analysis was employed to characterize the migration flows between municipalities as a directed graph, and to compute measures like reciprocity (the tendency of moves from $A \rightarrow B$ to be matched by

moves from B→A). We developed dynamic visualizations - network maps - for each year, to illustrate spatial patterns of migration flows. The network visualizations help reveal structural patterns (such as clusters of well-connected regions and the bidirectional nature of exchanges) that might be obscured in tabular data. All analyses were conducted with CBS microdata in a secure environment, using R for statistical computation. By integrating granular administrative data with survey information, our approach provides an unusually detailed view of internal migration dynamics in the Netherlands.

Results

Demographic Profile of Internal Migrants

Over the 2009–2022 period, slightly more than one in four Netherlands residents changed municipality at least once. This indicates that internal migration is a common experience, affecting a substantial share of the population. We first examine how these internal migrants are distributed across demographic groups compared to the overall population. Key attributes include gender, age group, standardized income in quartiles, education level, and migration background (native or with migration background). Several demographic trends are evident: the population is aging (the 0–18 age group declined in size, while the 51–65 group grew) and becoming more educated on average (higher educational attainment levels increased). The share of residents born outside the Netherlands has also risen modestly over the period. These shifts reflect broader societal changes like population aging and increased educational participation. Further details on related trends in the Dutch population are available at: <https://www.cbs.nl/en-gb/society/population>.

We begin by relating overall population figures to migration frequencies. In Figure 1 we plot frequency of migrations in groups (right vertical axis, in blue) per person per group (horizontal axis) against that group’s average population size over 2009–2022 (secondary vertical axis).

Figure 1 Migration frequency in groups vs. population groups sizes, 2009-2022

(Source: Authors)

The figure captures both migration frequencies and population sizes across various demographic and socio-economic groups in the Netherlands from 2009 to 2022, visualising how often individuals in each group changed municipality during that period. However, it's important to interpret the image with caution: due to inconsistencies in data availability across years—especially for some characteristics like migration background—not all groups are equally represented throughout the entire period. For example, gender is available for the full population, while migration background is missing in some years, leading to lower total counts in that segment. This results in apparent mismatches in bar heights between groups even though they originate from the same overall dataset. So, while the trends and comparisons within each category are meaningful, the absolute totals may vary slightly due to partial data coverage across different years.

Several insights emerge from the figure. Younger adults are far more migratory than other age groups. Those aged 19–30 (and to a lesser extent 31–40) have high migration totals despite being smaller segments of the population. By contrast, children (0–18) and older adults (50+, especially 65+) have fewer moves relative to their large population size. This pattern aligns with Sjaastad's (1962) human capital investment theory, which views migration as an investment with higher returns when made early in life. Younger people are more mobile as they pursue general education and flexible career paths, while older individuals often hold location-specific skills that limit their mobility (see also Faggian et al. 2015).

Similar patterns to those for age appear for socio-economic groups. The lowest income quartile (Q1) and the highest income quartile (Q4) each generated more migrations than their share of the population, whereas middle income groups were comparatively less mobile. This U-shaped pattern aligns with classic migration theories. According to Sjaastad (1962), migration can be viewed as an investment in human capital, and individuals with higher income and education levels are more likely to move in pursuit of better job opportunities, amenities, or quality of life — such as access to urban infrastructure, prestigious schools, or career advancement. At the opposite end, Piore's (1979) dual labour market theory suggests that low-income individuals often hold unstable or low-wage jobs and may be structurally required to migrate frequently in order to maintain employment, particularly in sectors like agriculture, logistics, or temporary service work. This is further supported by insights from behavioural economics, where "survival migration" is driven by even marginal gains in living standards or access to welfare, with migration serving as a necessary strategy for coping with economic insecurity (Coulter et al., 2016).

Internal migration shows a near-linear pattern with respect to education: the higher the level of educational attainment, the greater the mobility. People with the highest education levels were among the most mobile groups, despite not being the largest population segment. Those with low education had fewer moves per capita, possibly due to fewer incentives or resources to relocate. As Schwartz (1976) noted, "the area searched increases with education," as more highly educated individuals are often seeking better-paying, more specialized, and thus geographically scarcer positions. This compels them to widen their job search radius, often competing in national or even international labour markets rather than local ones. The risks associated with migration are also lower for highly educated people: if they do not secure their ideal job, they can still access a broader range of employment opportunities, including those typically available to the less educated (Faggian et al., 2015).

Meanwhile, individuals with a migration background (first- or second-generation immigrants) did not show a dramatic difference from natives in total moves relative to their share — both groups' points are not far from the diagonal, indicating their migration activity is roughly proportional to their population size. This finding contrasts with what some strands of

the migration literature suggest — namely, that ethnic minorities are often more mobile due to factors like labour market precarity, housing instability, or weaker social ties to place (Faggian et al., 2015). However, our data refer to migration background rather than ethnicity, which includes a wide spectrum of individuals with diverse socio-economic statuses and levels of integration. As such, the expected higher mobility among ethnic minorities may not appear here, either because migration background is too broad a category or because many with a migration background are well-integrated and exhibit similar mobility patterns to natives.

Overall, the demographic profile shows that Dutch internal migration is highly concentrated among young adults and extremes of the income and education spectra.

Age and Life Stage Trends

Beyond group totals, we zoom in on innate attributes such as age and gender to see how migration frequencies have evolved over time. Figure 2 breaks down the total number of internal migrations by five-year age bands and by sex, across the 2009–2022 period. Each line traces the total number of moves made by people of a given age group (male and female separately) over the 13-year period. The highest lines correspond to individuals aged 20–29, who moved far more often than other ages.

Figure 2. Total migration frequencies in the period 2009–2022, by age (5-year groups) and gender.

(Source: Authors)

Notably, women aged ~20–25 had slightly higher mobility early in the age span, while men peaked a few years later. After age 30, mobility declines sharply, reaching a minimum in mid-life, but then ticks up again around the retirement age (mid/late 60s). Overall internal migration volumes have grown over time (the lines for most age groups trend upward), indicating an upward shift in mobility even as the population gets older. Young adults in their twenties have the highest migration rates of any age group, and this dominance became even more pronounced over time. In particular, migration activity among 20–24 year-olds and 25–29 year-olds increased steadily, peaking toward the end of the period. This likely reflects growing participation in higher education (many students move to attend university) and increased job mobility early in careers. Interestingly, women in their early twenties showed a slightly higher peak in moves than men of the same age. This could suggest that young women tend to make major life transitions (such as pursuing education or starting jobs in a new city) a bit earlier on average than young men, who peak in mobility in their mid-to-late twenties.

After around age 30, migration frequency drops for both men and women, as people settle into careers and family life. The lowest mobility is observed in the late 30s through 50s age range. However, toward the end of working age, there is a modest uptick: people in their 60s (approaching retirement) show a slight increase in migration rates. Some of this could be retirees relocating (e.g. downsizing homes or moving to be closer to family or amenities). Over the 13-year period, overall internal migration counts have risen even as the population aged. The fact that middle-aged and even older groups show some increase in moves suggests that mobility is not just a young person’s phenomenon – an aging society can still experience rising internal migration if older individuals become a bit more mobile than in the past. External factors may also play a role; for example, broader trends in the housing market and evolving regional labour conditions throughout the 2010s might have influenced mid-life relocations. Although not directly measured in this study, such contextual factors have been identified in previous literature as relevant for mobility decisions (see the Introduction for references). In summary, the data indicate that while young adults remain the engine of internal migration, there is a broad-based increase in mobility across multiple life stages in recent years.

Migration Network and Reciprocity

Beyond individual characteristics, internal migration can be viewed as a network of flows between locations. We mapped all inter-municipal moves in the Netherlands as a directed network, where nodes are municipalities and an edge from A to B represents people moving from municipality A to B in a given year. The network visualization is available at <https://bit.ly/NL-INTERNAL-MIGRATION>, and the close-up view to the most intensely connected regions is shown in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3 Network of internal migration (Randstad region) in the Netherlands

(Source: Authors.)

This visualization reveals that there are strong exchange flows among the major cities and their surrounding areas – in this example, the Randstad cities (Amsterdam, Rotterdam, The Hague, Utrecht) form a well-integrated cluster with many people swapping residences back and forth among these and nearby municipalities. Overall, moves are more frequent between geographically closer cities, and the network structure remains fairly stable over time: the main corridors of migration (e.g. between the Randstad and certain regional centres) persist throughout 2009–2022.

Moreover, one prominent feature of the Netherlands’ migration network is its high reciprocity. This pattern is well known, particularly as it was laid out in what is often considered the earliest theoretical work on internal migration: Ravenstein’s (1885) “laws of migration,” which include the idea that each migration flow tends to generate a counterflow. Here we quantify this reciprocity “precisely”, by calculating the proportion of moves that are returned, using the weighted reciprocity formula as defined in the *igraph* package for the R software used for the very calculation (Csárdi and Nepusz, 2006):

$$r_w = \frac{\sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} \min(w_{ij}, w_{ji})}{\sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} w_{ij}},$$

where w_{ij} represents the weight of the directed edge from node i to node j —in this case, the number of individuals migrating from municipality i to municipality j .

This measure sums the smaller migration flow between each pair of municipalities, capturing reciprocated movements, and divides by the total migration across all pairs. The global reciprocity of the Dutch internal migration network was about 0.76 (or 76%) when averaged over 2009–2022. In other words, for every 100 people who moved from one municipality to another, roughly 76 people moved in the reverse direction within the same timeframe.

It’s worth noting that reciprocity around 0.75 is quite high as compared to what has been observed in other European countries. Former studies have found lower reciprocity in internal migration networks – for instance, around 0.60 in Austria and 0.50 in Croatia (Pitoski et al. 2024). The Netherlands’ flat geography, short distances between cities, and uniform infrastructure likely facilitate this high level of exchange.

Given the complexity of the migration network characteristics identified here, as well as the relatively uncommon application of advanced network analysis methods in migration studies, the observed patterns warrant deeper and more comprehensive network analyses. Recent empirical studies (e.g., Pitoski et al. 2023) have highlighted significant methodological challenges when migration networks are abstracted as static structures. For instance, when using total annual migration flows as edge weights, extreme self-loop weights and high reciprocity substantially limit the interpretability and reliability of many established network indicators and algorithms.

Although researchers typically apply statistical inference techniques to justify network simplifications, such as removing looping edges prior to applying network metrics, the outcomes from these static abstractions still require careful interpretation. Advancing towards dynamic space-time network abstractions can effectively overcome these methodological issues—self-loops and high reciprocity—thus offering more robust analytical frameworks not

only for migration networks but for various other network contexts as well. This will be the focus of our future research.

Migration Distances and Spatial Mobility

At this point, we restrict the analysis to the SSW data for ease of computation, without substantial loss of generality, as the SSW constitutes a random sample of the Dutch population aged 15 and over³. Using the SSW sample data, we have analysed the distances that people move and how these relate to their characteristics. For each individual who relocated, we calculated the straight-line distance between their origin and destination municipalities for each move (using coordinates). These distances were summed per person over 2009–2022 and compared to how many moves the person made.

Figure 4 presents a set of charts showing average migration frequency and average distance moved for different categories: gender, age group, income quartile, education level, and migration background. Each chart uses consistent dual y-axes to display migration frequency (primary vertical axes) and the distance moved (secondary vertical axes).

Figure 4. Migration frequencies and distances by individual attributes, SSW respondents (2009-2022)

(Source: Authors)

³ The only implication is for the youngest age group in Figure 4: although the figure is labelled “0–18”, the underlying SSW data include only respondents aged 15–18. We retain the conventional 0–18 label to keep the age bands comparable with the register-based statistics and because moves made by 15–18-year-olds typically reflect household decisions taken by their parents or guardians. Given the relatively small size of this group, this approximation is unlikely to materially affect our results.

Several patterns emerge. First, individuals in the lowest income quartile tend to move less frequently but cover longer distances on average when they do move. In fact, low-income movers logged some of the greatest average distances, comparable to the highest-educated group. One explanation is that lower-income people may need to relocate farther afield to find affordable living situations or job opportunities (for example, moving from an expensive urban area to a cheaper region). On the other hand, the highest educated individuals also moved long distances, likely pursuing specialized jobs or higher studies that require going to specific cities or regions.

Another finding is that age affects move distance: moves tend to be longest for young adults and then shorten with age. People under 30 often make long-distance moves (such as going to a faraway university or a different part of the country for work). After around age 30, average distances drop off sharply. Older movers (e.g. over 40) tend to relocate over much shorter ranges, possibly preferring to stay within the same region or province. Additionally, we see that those with middle levels of education (e.g. some secondary or vocational training) had among the shortest move distances. This group may have less incentive or ability to move far, compared to either highly educated professionals or those with low education seeking better opportunities. Differences by gender were relatively minor in terms of distance – men and women showed similar distance patterns when other factors were held constant. Likewise, the distances moved by native Dutch and those with a migration background did not differ substantially on average.

Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive look at internal migration in the Netherlands over a recent 13-year period, highlighting who moves, how far, and how these movements form broader patterns. Our findings confirm that internal migration is a major factor in the country's demographic dynamics – roughly 4.7 million people (25% of the population) changed municipalities between 2009 and 2022. Young adults drive much of this mobility, especially those in their twenties who move for education, jobs, or family formation. We also found that both the lowest-income and highest-income individuals are relatively mobile (for different reasons: necessity vs. opportunity), and higher education is associated with greater mobility. At the same time, life stage plays a big role: mobility peaks in the mid-20s and then declines with age, although there are signs of increased moves even among middle-aged and older groups in recent years.

The network of NL internal migration flows is highly reciprocal and balanced. Most moves between any two cities are matched by moves in the opposite direction, reflecting a relatively balanced exchange of population across regions. This reciprocity (around 75%) is higher than in many other countries, suggesting that the Netherlands' evenly distributed opportunities and short distances encourage two-way movement. We observed a slight drop in reciprocity during the COVID-19 period, but the overall structure of migration flows remained resilient. Additionally, we saw that while long-distance moves are relatively uncommon, the individuals who do move over long ranges tend to be a specific profile (young, often with higher education but low current income). This indicates that internal migration can contribute to redistributing human capital – for instance, educated youth from all parts of the country relocating for opportunities, which has implications for regional development. In conclusion, internal migration in the Netherlands is widespread and touches all segments of society, but its intensity and character vary considerably by age and socio-economic status. The period 2009–2022 saw increasing mobility and sustained exchange between regions, underlining the importance of internal migration in shaping local populations.

Policymakers and planners should recognize that facilitating internal mobility (through housing, transportation, and regional opportunities) is vital for balancing demographic and economic pressures. The high reciprocity of flows is a positive sign of interconnected communities, but emerging trends (like certain regions consistently gaining or losing residents) should be monitored. Future research could build on these findings by examining more nuanced factors (e.g. housing market dynamics, health, or social networks) and by integrating short- distance moves (within municipalities) to fully capture mobility. Overall, our analysis demonstrates that looking inward at internal migration is as important as looking at immigration when considering the Netherlands' population trends and cohesion.

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